

Karolina Zielska

Thought leadership paper

“What an auditor should know about SAP”

BACKGROUND INFORMATION

SAP is a phenomenal accounting program that is almost 50 years old. SAP was started in 1972 by five former IBM employees in the city of Mannheim (Germany). SAP AG was the official name since 2005.

SAP abbreviation stands for *Systems, Applications and Products in Data Processing* (German name: *Systeme, Anwendungen und Produkte*). It is an ERP software (ERP stands for *Enterprise Resource Planning*) that integrates several business applications. There are different ERP available, SAP is one of them, the other ones are for example Oracle or Sage.

SAP is a three tier application architecture, which is described as R/3. R/3 is represented by three elements – Database, Application server, Presentation client.

One of advantages of SAP system is for example the fact that SAP software is customizable, it can be altered to meet almost any enterprise requirement. Moreover, SAP is a system that allows real time management and tracking of finance, sales, production, accounting and HR matters in an enterprise. It is like an online system, you can access this system sitting in any country/ any place. Thirdly, it integrates data from all departments in company – sales, purchases, HR, reporting.

SAP is divided into modules accordingly to the list below:

1. Financial
 - a. Financial Accounting
 - b. Controlling
 - c. Asset Accounting
 - d. Funds Management
2. Logistics
 - a. Sales and Distribution
 - b. Materials Management
 - c. Project Systems
 - d. Plant Management
3. Human Resources
 - a. Human Capital management

SHORTCUTS FOR DOCUMENT TYPE THAT ARE THE SAME FOR ANY AUDIT CLIENT

In SAP there are default values programmed before and they cannot be changed. So in any company that we will be auditing the accounting team will have the same default values for the following document types, so we can use this terminology and those values when we are talking with audit clients and we ask them for some underlying documentation that is needed during audit.

How to access the list of default values? You are advised to follow the instructions below:

- ➔ In search bar enter “/nspro”
- ➔ Click “SAP reference IMG”
- ➔ SAP Customizing Implementation Guide -> Financial Accounting Global Settings -> Document -> Default values -> Define default values -> Display

The screenshot shows a SAP table titled "Default Values: Document Type and Posting Key". The table has four columns: TCode, Transaction Text, Doc.Type, and PK. It lists various transaction codes and their corresponding document types and posting keys.

TCode	Transaction Text	Doc.Type	PK
F-01	Enter Sample Document	AB	
F-02	Enter G/L Account Posting	SA	40
F-04	Post with Clearing	SA	
F-05	Post Foreign Currency Valuation	SA	40
F-06	Post Incoming Payments	DZ	
F-07	Post Outgoing Payments	KZ	
F-18	Payment with Printout	DZ	
F-19	Reverse Statistical Posting	DA	
F-20	Reverse Bill Liability	DA	
F-21	Enter Transfer Posting	DA	
F-22	Enter Customer Invoice	DR	01
F-25	Reverse Check/Bill of Exch.	DA	
F-26	Incoming Payments Fast Entry	DZ	
F-27	Enter Customer Credit Memo	DG	11
F-28	Post Incoming Payments	DZ	
F-29	Post Customer Down Payment	DZ	
F-30	Post with Clearing	DA	
F-31	Post Outgoing Payments	DZ	
F-33	Post Bill of Exchange Usage	DA	
F-34	Post Collection	DA	
F-35	Post Forfaiting	DA	
F-36	Bill of Exchange Payment	DZ	09
F-37	Customer Down Payment Request	DZ	
F-38	Enter Statistical Posting	DA	09
F-39	Clear Customer Down Payment	DA	
F-40	Bill of Exchange Payment	KZ	39
F-41	Enter Vendor Credit Memo	KG	21
F-42	Enter Transfer Posting	AB	
F-43	Enter Vendor Invoice	KR	31
F-46	Reverse Refinancing Acceptance	KA	

STANDARD REPORTS

From our position, auditor's position, an important feature of SAP is the one with standard reports, that is standard reports in general ledger accounting, accounts receivable and accounts payable, balance sheet and profit & loss statement.

There are general financial statements available that compare actual to actual or plan to actual, cash flow statement. These ones are useful for management to analyze company's general performance and for us, auditors, to assess company's state.

There is a very useful kind of report that is called "drilled down report". When we have any position in balance sheet, for example cash balance, we can click on it and go deeper into details and see General Ledger Account Line Item Display. We can see all transactions that sum up to this balance, we can drill

down to the original document. These are standard reports so any company will have it and we can always demand them during audit.

Account balances is another type of standard reports.

Reports that are standard are also for Accounts Receivable and accounts Payable. Under "Reporting" click "Accounts Receivable" -> "Information system" -> "Reports for Accounts Receivable Accounting".

It might be very useful to know that any client using SAP can generate for us customer balances or customer sales reports. It is also very easy for our client to generate due date analysis for open items or customer payment history to assess his credibility. The whole list of available receivables reports are on the screen below:

All available reports are visible in "Information systems" -> "Accounting" -> "Financial Accounting" -> and here are all reports "General Ledger" (with balance sheet or chart of accounts), "Accounts receivable" (with open items which we often use in audit, account list, account balances), "Accounts Payable", "Fixed Assets"

Useful SAP function for dual control

During interim audit assignments we analyze business environment and discuss processes at client's company, we look "what can go wrong" and which control is in place to mitigate this risk. One of them is a dual control so when two people are checking something. When we discuss posting process we should be aware that SAP enables dual control by its functions – hold and park documents.

User can click "Hold" when he is not sure about transaction, it is possible that their client will back off from the transaction. Such document do not receive a document number, only a temporary name.

On the other hand "parked" documents receive a document number, they are used when we are sure that the underlying transaction occurred and we only want to leave it for a supervisor to revise it, accept and post. Parked document, e.g. invoice, can be changed, amount can be changed. But the posting date remains unchanged.

FV60 is a transaction code for parking a document.

PROCESSES RELATED TO MONTH-END AND YEAR-END CLOSING

Automatic Payment Program

This part of SAP answers the problem of how to make quick payments to our vendors and customers – payments to customers when they are returning items or they overpaid us earlier or our customer is also our supplier at the same time. Automatic Payment Program is often used in the situation when the Headquarter is responsible for regulating outstanding invoices at the end of month for all of its regional companies. The Headquarter does not have to go through hundreds or thousands of unpaid invoices for each company, it only runs this Automatic Payment Program and with one click all invoices are cleared, paid. While setting up Automatic payment Program in SAP user is able to set up maximum amount of invoice that can be cleared with this program.

The transaction code to configure Automatic Payment Program is FBZP.

The transaction code to run the Automatic Payment Program is F110.

Automatic Dunning Program

This program is made to send notices to the customers who do not pay on time. Set up options for dunning procedure allow us to define “dunning interval in days”, so if it is 14 it means that every 14 days when the invoice is still unpaid the dunning notice will be automatically sent, 14 days pass and notice is sent, another 14 days pass and invoice is still unpaid so the next notice is sent and so on every 14 days. We can also set up “line item grace periods” so how many days we give the customer as sign of our grace, so if customer has 30 days to pay invoice and we set up 2 days of grace period, then It means that after 32 days the first automatic dunning notice will be sent. We can set up interest and additionally also dunning charge so something like a penalty.

The transaction code to configure Automatic Dunning Program is FBMP.

The transaction code to run the Automatic Dunning Program is F150.

Clearing documents at month-end

1. Partial payment

Let's imagine that there is an invoice for 18.000 EUR but customer pays only 10.000 EUR. We go to the invoice and click on worksheet “Partial Pmt (payment)” to enter this 10.000 EUR. Then when we click on the line item, on this invoice, the document will be visible as open, because some balance is still remaining. Only when the customer will make full payment the document will be closed. Until then when we click on “Customer Line Item Display” we will see two lines: invoice for 18.00 EUR and partial payment 10.000- EUR. When remaining 8.000 EUR will be paid it will be closed and clearing document reference will be the same next to all those three lines (18.000, 10.000 and 8.000 lines).

2. Residual items

It is another way of clearing documents. Partial payment was a 2 step process when with receiving partial payment the original invoice was not cleared. But when we have a vendor invoice for e.g. 30.000 EUR, pay him only 20.000 EUR and we enter “Residual Items” 10.000 EUR in such worksheet, then the document is cleared and a new document is shown as open. Document number of the original invoice

is closed with clearing document, let's say clearing document number 102, and the clearing document 102 is visible as open with the amount of 10.000 EUR.

Residual payment processing clears original invoice with incoming amount and creates a new line item for remaining outstanding amount.

ⁱ All SAP screens are from Udemy lecture "SAP FICO (FINANCIAL ACCOUNTING & MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING", Rana W Mehmood